

Influence of Interest and Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in the Concept of Motion in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of interest and strategy (Meta-conceptual and Scaffolding Learning Strategies) on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in the concept of Motion in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. A sample of 192, SS2 Physics students was randomly selected from three schools. Three research questions were answered with mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two validated, researcher-constructed instruments were used to collect data for Physics Interest Scale with a coefficient of 0.71 obtained using Cronbach Alpha (α) reliability test, and Motion Performance Test with a reliability coefficient of 0.89 obtained using Kuder-Richardson formula method (K-R 20). The mean and standard deviations (SD) were used in answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used in testing the research hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. These results indicate that Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy enhanced students' interest in Physics more than Scaffolding Learning Strategy and Lecture method. There is no significant difference between the male and female students with respect to their interest in Physics. There is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' interest in Physics. Also, interest and performance can be improved by innovative teaching methods. It was therefore recommended that Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy be used by teachers to teach motion in schools to improve students' interest and performance.

Keywords: *Interest, student performance, Physics, Meta- Conceptual and Scaffolding Learning Strategies.*

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Introduction

The study of Physics enables students and practitioners in the field to understand the changing and existing world and also get a better knowledge of the universal laws. The concept of physics offers the students the opportunity to think critically, reason analytically and acquire the spirit of inquiry due to its abstract nature, therefore it is necessary for the teacher to look out for a teaching method that is interactive and engaging (Nwafor, 2018). The knowledge of Physics develops in students, the scientific and technological knowledge, skills and attitudes which will assist them to make decisions based on observation and experimentation (Bwala, et al., 2024). Omiola et al. (2020) stressed the fact that students understand the concepts of the sciences better when they know Physics. Physics has so many branches, and the concept of Motion is taught under mechanics, which is one of the branches of Physics. In most cases, in describing Motion, it involves the use of symbols, graphs and equations. Therefore, there is a need to make the teaching and learning of Physics simple, to increase students' interest and performance in the subject.

The progress of students in their education can be monitored through their performance in school, and the performance can be measured through the giving of tests , exams (Bileya et al., 2021). However, some researchers have argued that interest has a significant very low positive effect on students' academic performance (Awodun et al., 2013; Femi-Adeoye & Adekunle, 2016).

Interest is seen as an increase in students' attention, concentration with great motivation for students to learn better (Mazer, 2020). Interest is a driver for higher learning outcome and for effective teaching and learning, strategies that will arouse students' interest in Physics should be considered. On the issue of students' interest in Physics, Okafor (2020) revealed that student's interest predict about 57% of academic achievement scores of secondary school students in Physics and students with high interest in Physics are expected to excel in their academics. Kpolovie et al (2014) revealed that students' interest significantly contributed to about 21.6% of students' academic achievement.

On the issue of gender, Afonja (2022) defined gender as a socially constructed concept based on the assumed position that a group of humans should possess. According to Okeke (2016), gender is referred to as a socially constructed role and socially learned behaviors and expectations associated with males and females. Still on gender, Adesoji (2018) worked on students' ability levels and the effectiveness of problem-solving instructional strategies on the interests of students of different ability levels. The results show that a significant difference does not exist in the performance of students across the different groups. Morgan and Aboagye (2022) investigated students' interest in Physics with regard to gender, school type, and programme of study. It was found that students' interest in Physics was generally moderate and male students had more interest in Physics than the female students (Zhang, 2019). Similarly, Technical students were more interested in Physics than General Science students, whereas students from Boys' only schools were found to have higher interest in Physics than students from mixed and Girls schools (Zhang, 2019). Again, Aina and Akintunde (2013) who worked on the analysis of gender performance in Physics in colleges of

Education found that the performance of gender is not gender bias; though male students performed better than the female students.

On the issue of strategy, Akara and Avwiri, (2025) work on the effect of instructional strategy on Physics students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State and found out that flex instructional strategy had a significant effect on the mean performance of students in Physics. Nwakile (2023) worked on comparative effects of multiple teaching methods on academic achievement and interest of upper basic education students in social studies in Anambra State and found out that the discussion method and demonstration improved the academic achievement and interest of upper basic education students, followed by the lecture method in the teaching and learning of social studies. Matthew et al (2022) worked on the effects of Jigsaw cooperative learning strategies on JCIS) students' interest and performance in social studies and found out that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores and mean interest scores of students taught using Jigsaw cooperative learning and conventional strategies. This research shows that teaching method have a great influence on students' interest and performance.

On the research on joint effect, Baser and Durmus (2010) worked on the effectiveness of computer supported verses real laboratory inquiry learning environments on the understanding of direct current electricity among pre-service elementary school teachers and found significant interaction between gender and instructional treatment on students' academic achievement and interest in current electricity, while Obafemi (2015) who worked on application level of the concept of light waves with Physics students revealed a significant interaction of gender and strategy on students' performance. However, Avwiri and Uwadieke (2026) worked on effect of meta-conceptual and scaffolding instruction on senior secondary students Physics achievement and found out that there is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' performance in Physics.

Onah & Achufusi (2022) examined the Effect of Meta-conceptual teaching approach on Students' academic achievement and interest in Quantum Physics in Enugu Education Zone. The results showed that gender has no significant influence on the academic achievement of students in Quantum Physics and also found out that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching method on students' interest in Physics (Onah, 2022).

A well-planned scaffolding allows the students to perform the entire task with little or no support from their instructor since it can model and manage the learning environment effectively. Olufunke (2020) worked on the effects of Scaffolding teaching strategy on students' academic achievement in secondary school Chemistry in Ekiti State and found a significant achievement brought about by the experimental scaffolding strategy. Onukwube and Okigbo (2022) investigated the effect of scaffolding instructional strategy (SIS) on secondary school students' interest in mathematics in Otucha education zone of Anambra State and found out that the use of SIS in teaching SS2 students' geometry significantly enhanced their interest scores compared to when the conventional lecture method was used to teach the students. The study also showed that the male students had a significantly high interest in geometry than the female students when taught geometry with SIS.

Meta-Conceptual Knowledge is an advanced form of learning and understanding that involves awareness and insight into how concepts themselves are structured, developed, and applied into education. Nwankwo et al (2019) investigated the effect

of an interactive and learner-friendly Meta-Conceptual teaching approach on students' achievement in Physics and found out that there is a significant effect of the Meta-Conceptual teaching approach (MTA) on students' achievement in Physics, this implies that MTA can enhance students' performance in Physics.

Statement of the Problem

WAEC Chief Examiner (2019) reported the poor performances of Physics students in the West Africa examination results, and the challenges faced by students' misunderstanding of some Physics concepts, including equations of motion. This misconception demonstrates the abstract nature of mathematical concepts in the theoretical background. Thus, there is the need to ameliorate these challenges to improve the students' performance. Could the instructional delivery used by teachers be a factor contributing to the poor performance of students?

Could the students' interest in the subject affect their performance in physics? Therefore, this study aims to investigate the influence of interest and strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in the concept of Motion.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine the influence of interest and strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in motion. The specific objectives guiding the study are:

1. Investigate the difference in the mean Interest scores of students taught using Meta- Conceptual, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using Lecture in the concept of motion.
2. Examine the difference in the mean Interest scores of male and female students taught using Meta- Conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using Lecture Method in the concept of motion.
3. Examine the joint effect of teaching Strategy and gender on students' Interest in the concept of motion.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught using Meta- Conceptual, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using the Lecture Method in the concept of motion?
2. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught using Meta- conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using the Lecture Method in the concept of motion?
3. What is the joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' Interest in the concept of motion?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses, which were tested at 0.05 levels of significance, guided this study:

HO1: There is no significant difference among the students taught using the Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught using the Scaffolding Learning Strategy, and those taught using the Lecture Method with respect to their interest in the concept of motion.

HO2: There is no significant difference between the male and female students with respect to their interest in the concept of motion.

HO3 There is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' interest in the concept of motion.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The independent variable is instructional strategy, the dependent variable is students' interest in the concept of Motion while the moderating variable is gender. The study area is Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 3 schools. A sample of 192 senior secondary school students was selected from a population of 3263. Meta-Conceptual Learning and Scaffolding Learning strategy are the experimental group while the Lecture Method is the control group. Two validated, researcher-constructed instruments were used to collect data, Physics Interest Scale, with a coefficient of 0.71 obtained using the Cronbach Alpha (α) reliability test, and the Motion Performance Test, with a reliability coefficient of 0.89 obtained using the Kuder-Richardson formula method (K-R 20). The Physics Interest Scale (PIS) and Motion Performance Test were administered to each group before and after the strategy was used to teach the students. The mean and standard deviations (SD) were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. The Motion Performance Test was used to gather data on students' performance. It contained 25 multiple-choice questions with options A-E. Each question scored 4 marks, giving a total of 100%. Physics Interest Scale (PIS) was a modified Likert scale, scored 4, 3, 2, 1 for Strongly Agree, Agree and Disagree, and Strongly Disagree, respectively.

Results

Research Questions 1

What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught using Meta-Conceptual, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using the Lecture Method in the concept of motion?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Interest Level Classified by Teaching Strategy

Strategy		Pre-Interest	Post-Interest	Gain
Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy	Mean	19.1429	50.9429	31.8000
	Std. Deviation	4.0835	12.2378	12.9867
	N	70	70	70
Scaffolding Learning Strategy	Mean	13.0727	42.4545	29.3818
	Std. Deviation	3.0298	12.2638	12.5985
	N	55	55	55
Lecture Method	Mean	15.3881	40.2239	24.8358
	Std. Deviation	2.9437	14.0074	14.2856
	N	67	67	67

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' interest level classified by instructional strategy. It shows that the students taught motion using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy had a mean gain of 31.80 and standard deviation of 12.99 ($M_g = 31.80$, $SD = 12.99$), the students taught Physics concepts using

Scaffolding Learning Strategy had a mean gain of 29.38 and standard deviation of 12.60 ($M_g = 29.38$, $SD = 12.60$). In contrast, the students taught Physics concepts using the Lecture method had a mean gain of 24.84 and a standard deviation of 14.29 ($M_g = 24.84$, $SD = 14.29$). These results show that students taught the concept of Motion using a Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy had the highest interest level in the concept, followed by those taught using a Scaffolding Learning Strategy, while students taught using the Lecture method had the lowest interest level in the concept. These results indicate that Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy enhanced students' interest in the concept of motion more than Scaffolding Learning Strategy and the Lecture method.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught using Meta- conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught Scaffolding Learning Strategies, and those taught using the Lecture Method in the concept of Motion?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Interest Level Classified by Gender

Gender		Pre-Interest	Post-Interest	Gain
Male	Mean	15.3263	44.1263	28.8000
	Std. Deviation	3.7058	14.4688	14.3539
	N	95	95	95
Female	Mean	16.8454	45.4021	28.5567
	Std. Deviation	4.5674	12.9081	12.9123
	N	97	97	97

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' interest level classified by gender. It shows that the male students had a mean gain of 28.80 and standard deviation of 14.35 ($M_g = 28.80$, $SD = 14.35$) while the female students had a mean gain of 28.56 and standard deviation of 12.91 ($M_g = 28.56$, $SD = 12.91$). These results indicate that the male students had a higher interest in the concept of Motion than the female students (Morah, & Obafemi, 2026).

Research Question 3

What is the joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' Interest in the concept of Motion?

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Interest Level Classified by Teaching Strategy and Gender

Strategy	Gender		Pre-Interest	Post-Interest	Gain
Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy	Male	Mean	19.6842	51.8421	32.1579
		Std. Deviation	2.3346	13.5370	12.5178
		N	19	19	19
	Female	Mean	18.9412	50.6078	31.6667
		Std. Deviation	4.5713	11.8441	13.2766
		N	51	51	51
Scaffolding Learning Strategy	Male	Mean	12.4857	43.3714	30.8857
		Std. Deviation	2.6720	12.8934	13.7921
		N	35	35	35
	Female	Mean	14.1000	40.8500	26.7500

		Std. Deviation	3.4012	11.2122	9.9624
		N	20	20	20
Lecture Method	Male	Mean	15.7317	41.1951	25.4634
		Std. Deviation	2.7388	15.1859	15.2120
		N	41	41	41
	Female	Mean	14.8462	38.6923	23.8462
		Std. Deviation	3.2211	12.0425	12.9173
		N	26	26	26

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' interest level classified by teaching strategy and gender. It shows that the male students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy with the highest mean gain of 32.16 and standard deviation of 12.52 ($M_g = 32.16$, $SD = 12.52$) had the highest interest level, followed by the female students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy with the mean gain of 31.67 and standard deviation of 13.28 ($M_g = 31.67$, $SD = 13.28$), while the female students taught using Lecture Method with the mean gain of 23.85 and standard deviation of 12.92 ($M_g = 23.85$, $SD = 12.92$) had the least interest level. This result indicates that the male students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy had the highest interest in the concept of Motion, followed by the female students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy, while the female students taught using Lecture Method had the least interest level in the concept of motion.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference among the students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught using Scaffolding Learning Strategy, and those taught using Lecture Method with respect to their interest in the concept of Motion.

Table 4. Summary of One-way Analysis of Covariance of Students' Interest Level Classified by Teaching Strategy Using Pre-Interest as Covariate Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Post-Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4347.197 ^a	3	1449.066	8.675	0.000	0.122
Intercept	16847.819	1	16847.819	100.857	0.000	0.349
Pre-Interest	0.330	1	0.330	0.002	0.965	0.000
Strategy	3297.772	2	1648.886	9.871	0.000	0.095
Error	31404.719	188	167.046			
Total	420602.000	192				
Corrected Total	35751.917	191				

a. R Squared = 0.122 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.108)

Table 4: presents the summary of one-way Analysis of Covariance of students' interest level classified by teaching strategy using Pre-interest as Covariate. It reveals a value of $F_{2,188} = 9.871$, $p = 0.00$ ($p < 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.095 for the effect of teaching strategy on students' interest level in Physics. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference among the students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy, those taught using Scaffolding Learning Strategy, and those taught using Lecture Method with respect to their interest in the concept of

Motion. The partial eta squared value shows that teaching strategy had a medium effect on students' interest in the concept of Motion.

Table 5. Least Significant Difference Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Interest Level Classified by Teaching strategy Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Post-Interest						
(I) Strategy	(J) Strategy	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy	Scaffolding Learning Strategy	8.562*	2.863	0.003	2.914	14.211
	Lecture Method	10.765*	2.437	0.000	5.956	15.573
Scaffolding Learning Strategy	Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy	-8.562*	2.863	0.003	-14.211	-2.914
	Lecture Method	2.202	2.436	0.367	-2.603	7.008
Lecture Method	Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy	-10.765*	2.437	0.000	-15.573	-5.956
	Scaffolding Learning Strategy	-2.202	2.436	0.367	-7.008	2.603
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).						

Table 5. presents the Least Significant Difference Post hoc analysis of students' interest level classified by teaching strategy. It reveals a mean difference of 8.562 and a p-value of 0.003 ($p < 0.05$) between the effect of Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy and Scaffolding Learning Strategy, and a mean difference of 10.765 and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) between the effect of Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy and Lecture Method on students' interest in the concept of Motion. This result shows that the Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy brought in the highest mean difference of 10.765, thereby contributing most to the significance difference in the effect of the teaching strategies used on students' interest in the concept of Motion.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the male and female students with respect to their interest in the concept of Motion.

Table 6. Summary of One-way Analysis of Covariance of Students' Interest Level Classified by Gender Using Pre-interest as Covariate Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Post-Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1058.699 ^a	2	529.349	2.884	0.058	0.030
Intercept	15459.341	1	15459.341	84.219	0.000	0.308
Pre-Interest	980.586	1	980.586	5.342	0.022	0.027
Gender	9.273	1	9.273	0.051	0.822	0.000
Error	34693.218	189	183.562			
Total	420602.000	192				
Corrected Total	35751.917	191				
a. R Squared = 0.030 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.019)						

Table 6. presents the summary of one–way Analysis of Covariance of students’ interest classified by gender using Pre-interest as Covariate. It reveals a value of $F_{1,189} = 0.051$, $p = 0.822$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.000 for the effect of gender on students’ interest in Physics. The null hypothesis is therefore retained, indicating that there is no significant difference between the male and female students with respect to their interest in Physics. The partial eta squared value shows that gender did not affect students’ interest in the concept of Motion.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students’ interest in the concept of Motion.

Table 7. Summary of 3X2 Analysis of Covariance of Students’ Interest Level Classified by Teaching Strategy and Gender Using Pre-interest as Covariate Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Post-Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4548.784 ^a	6	758.131	4.495	0.000	0.127
Intercept	16083.328	1	16083.328	95.356	0.000	0.340
Pre-Interest	0.249	1	0.249	0.001	0.969	0.000
Strategy	3148.001	2	1574.000	9.332	0.000	0.092
Gender	183.330	1	183.330	1.087	0.299	0.006
Strategy * Gender	14.910	2	7.455	0.044	0.957	0.000
Error	31203.133	185	168.666			
Total	420602.000	192				
Corrected Total	35751.917	191				

a. R Squared = 0.127 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.099)

Table 7 presents the summary of the 3X2 Analysis of Covariance of students’ interest level classified by teaching strategy and gender using Pre-interest as a covariate. It reveals a value of $F_{2,185} = 7.455$, $p = 0.957$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.000 for the interaction of teaching strategy and gender on students’ interest in the concept of Motion. The null hypothesis is therefore retained, indicating that there is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students’ interest in Physics. The partial eta squared value also shows that teaching strategy and gender do not have any joint effect on students’ interest in the concept of Motion.

Discussion

The study revealed that the Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy significantly enhanced students’ interest in Physics more than the Scaffolding Learning Strategy and the Lecture method with the least interest level. This agrees with the work of Nwankwo et al (2019), who found out that the meta-conceptual teaching approach significantly enhances students’ achievement in Physics. It also agreed with Akara and Avwiri, (2025), who found that the flex instructional strategy had a significant effect on the mean performance of students in Physics. This also agrees with Nwakile (2023), who found out that the discussion and demonstration method greatly improves student achievement and interest of students in upper basic education more than the lecture method. This goes to support the fact that there are instructional strategies that could improve students’ performance and interest in their studies.

Teaching strategy had a medium effect on students' interest in Physics. This agrees with the work of kpolovie et al (2014) ; Okafor (2020); Onah and Achufusi (2022) that academic interest relatively and significantly contributed to the academic achievement of secondary school students.

The study also found out that the male students had a higher interest in the concept of Motion than the female students. This might be that boys like tough task and are interested in calculation. However, the difference in the interest level of the male and female students in the concept of Motion was not statistically significant, this goes to show that there was no gender bias in the course of teaching and learning. This also agrees with Adesoji (2018); Onah and Achufusi (2022) who found out that gender has no significant influence on the academic achievement of students in Quantum Physics. This disagrees with the works of Onukwube & Okigbo (2022) who found out that gender has a significant effect on the overall interest of students in geometry when taught with SIS in favour of males.

On the issue of joint effect, the male students taught using the Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy had the highest interest in Physics, followed by the female students taught using Meta-Conceptual Learning Strategy, while the female students taught using the Lecture Method had the least interest level in Physics. There was however, no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' interest in Physics. This agrees with the work of Onah & Achufusi (2022) who found out that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching method on students' interest in Physics it also agrees with the work of Avwiri and Uwadieke (2026) who revealed that there is no significant joint effect of teaching strategy and gender on students' performance in Physics. However, the work contradicts the findings of Baser and Durmus, (2010) who found significant interaction between gender and instructional treatment on students' academic achievement and interest in current electricity, and Obafemi (2015) who also revealed a significant interaction of gender and strategy on students' performance in the application level of the concept of light waves.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of interest and strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in Motion, It was deduced that the Meta- conceptual Learning Strategy made the students to understand question faster and respond sharply thereby arousing their interest and performance in Motion. There is no significant difference between the male and female students with respect to their interest in Physics, this goes to show that without bias during the course of teaching and learning, both the male and female students can learn equally. Though, Meta-conceptual and the Scaffolding Learning Strategies have enabled students' performance and interest from past reviewed, however this study gives credits to Meta-conceptual teaching strategy which has effectively enhanced the students' performance and interest in Motion.

Recommendations

Based on the implications and findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. To enhance students' interest in motion, the use of Meta- conceptual Learning Strategy should be used by Physics teachers in the teaching and learning of motion, since it has been proven to be effective.
2. Federal/ and State governments and other relevant professional bodies should organize and sponsor seminars, conferences, workshops or refresher courses on the use of Meta- conceptual Strategy to improve students' interest and performance in Physics.
3. Physics educators involved in the curriculum planning and development should restructure and include in the Senior Secondary School Physics Syllabus and textual materials that should recommend the use of Meta- conceptual strategy.
4. Federal and State governments and other relevant professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN); Curriculum Organization of Nigeria (CON); Mathematic Association of Nigeria (MAN); Federal and State Ministry of Education should encourage both male and female teachers and students to work harder in Physics to discourage gender disparity.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in this research.

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